

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE LEGAL BASIS OF COOPERATION BETWEEN AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC AND THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Abstract

The legal basis of the relations between the republics of Azerbaijan, Georgia and Armenia and the European Union was established by the agreement on partnership and cooperation between the EU and the South Caucasus states, signed in Luxembourg on April 22, 1996. Although provisions related to political development, democracy and protection of human rights prevailed in the agreement, in general, the European Union did not hide that it gave the main priority to the economic sphere in relations with the South Caucasus. The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement consisted of 12 chapters, 105 articles and 5 annexes. Only 2 pages of the 70-page Agreement discuss the tools of political dialogue. In general, the purpose of TAS is to serve the development of security, stability and prosperous living in the region on the basis of strong mutually beneficial cooperation. In addition, the agreement was intended as a long-term strategy of the EU in the South Caucasus. It is a strategy of large-scale economic aid and cooperation, formally regulated by a number of political conditions. From this point of view, the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement is an important and to some extent indirect tool of the common foreign policy of the European Union. From the above, it can be concluded that the promising directions of cooperation between the parties have further developed during the period since the signing of the Agreement. According to Ambassador Kestutis Jankauskas, the representative of the European Union in Azerbaijan, Brussels focuses on cooperation with Azerbaijan in areas such as "green economy", small entrepreneurship, development of regions, support of education and healthcare. These were intended to help sustainable development in Azerbaijan. However, we know that TAS was signed for a period of 10 years and since the implementation period of the agreement ended in 2009, its implementation is extended for 1 month every year.

Keywords: European Union, partnership, Caspian, region, South Caucasus, cooperation.

Introduction

The legal basis of the relations between the republics of Azerbaijan, Georgia and Armenia and the European Union was established by the agreement on partnership and cooperation between the EU and the South Caucasus states, signed in Luxembourg on April 22, 1996. The agreement entered into force on July 1, 1999 after ratification by all signatory states. A number of other important contracts, agreements on bilateral cooperation, etc., have been signed between the Union and Azerbaijan. is also signed. The partnership and cooperation agreement is a general document covering relations between Azerbaijan and the European Union, its member states in trade, investment, economic legislation and cultural cooperation, immigration, prevention of illegal trade and other areas. According to the agreement, in order to conduct regular bilateral dialogue between Azerbaijan and the European Union, structures such as the Cooperation Council, Cooperation Committee, Inter-Parliamentary Cooperation Committee, Sub-Committee on Trade, Economy and Legal Affairs, and Sub-Committee on Energy, Transport and Environmental Affairs were to be established. The Cooperation Council defines the main directions of cooperation, and the Cooperation Committee was supposed to assist the Council by making recommendations. Subcommittees on trade, economic and legal issues, as well as energy, transport and environment were to operate under the cooperation committee.

Political expression of economic relations

For Azerbaijan, which takes the path of democratic development, relations with countries that have those values were considered one of the international factors for the protection and strengthening of Azerbaijan's state independence. [4, p. 10] The Republic of Azerbaijan, which had just regained its independence, was looking for ways out of extremely tense conditions, and was trying to find a partner in solving its problems, which was within the experience and influence of Western European states and its leading organizations. [6, p.29] In order to preserve and strengthen the independence of the state, resolve the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict in a peaceful way, and carry out reforms in the field of market economy, the leadership of Azerbaijan hoped to attract foreign investment to the country's economy. In the early days, relations with European organizations were established on the basis of technical and humanitarian programs. From 1991 to 2001, the EU provided Azerbaijan with EUR 333.9 million in aid, thereby becoming Azerbaijan's main international donor. [6, p. 29]

Despite the financial assistance of the European Union, until 1995, the organization did not have a general strategy for the South Caucasus, which hindered the normal development of relations with the countries of the region. On June 12, 1995, the EU Council gathered in Luxembourg adopted a project of assistance to the South Caucasus states in the period of democratic development and transition to a market economy. According to Samuel Lussac, a French expert on the South

Caucasus, "in the first stage, the EU paid more attention to Armenia and Georgia, and ignored the political relations with Azerbaijan. [16, p.65] In 1995, the opening of the representative office of the European Commission in Tbilisi, which provides for the development of Georgia and Armenia, proved this idea. The creation of a legal basis for the relations of the European Union with the countries of the South Caucasus led to a change in conditions. Such a basis was the "Agreement on Partnership and Cooperation" between the South Caucasus states and the European Union.

European foreign policy in the South Caucasus, in addition to the TACIS program, found its further institutionalism in the signing of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (PACE).

Although provisions related to political development, democracy and protection of human rights prevailed in the agreement, in general, the European Union did not hide that it gave the main priority to the economic sphere in relations with the South Caucasus. Within the framework of this agreement, 3 projects on bilateral relations, TACIS technical assistance project, TRASEKA regional project and INOGATE program have been developed so far. On November 23, 1999, a state commission was established for the expansion and regulation of relations with the EU. The national leader H. Aliyev approved this agreement in 1996 and indicated in his speech that the Agreement on Partnership and Cooperation signed today between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the European Union is a historical event of great importance for the young independent state of Azerbaijan. The agreement opens wide horizons for expanding and deepening comprehensive cooperation, strengthening international peace and security, principles of integration, protecting human rights, and achieving progress and effective cooperation throughout the European continent. [1, p. 145]

In 1992, the Council made a decision to start negotiations with all the states that emerged after the collapse of the USSR. The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement was signed with all the countries of the region for a minimum period of 10 years. The purpose of the agreement is to create an institutional legal basis for cooperation between the European Union and the countries of the region in all fields, except for the military and security fields. All the Agreements signed with South Caucasus and Central Asian countries have the same text, but they reflect the characteristics of other countries.

In order to understand the role of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement of the European Union in relation to the region, first of all, it is necessary to consider the characteristics of this type of documents, not its content.

TAS is one of the two components of the new "Eastern policy" of the European Union. After the collapse of the USSR and the communist camp, a united Europe faced the need to establish political relations with new states. First, the expansion of cooperation with the USSR, and then with the CIS countries, Central and Eastern European countries was the most important event of the last decade. However, when the Union was created, it was impossible to envisage such

an activity. After the recognition of the EU by the countries of the Council for Mutual Economic Assistance (CMEA), relations began to develop at an unprecedented speed.

Starting from the first stage of its development, the EU made a concrete difference between European countries and CIS countries. The agreements concluded with Central and Eastern European states were intended to lead to the idea of a "united Europe". The CIS countries were not considered as real candidates for EU membership in the near future (except for the Baltic countries).

The purpose of the agreement is to define a new framework for the development of bilateral relations. Being an alternative to the agreements signed with the countries of Central and Eastern Europe was very important in the context of the new "Eastern policy" of the EU.

The legal point of view is based on Articles 113 (133) and 235 (308) of the Treaty on European Union. They apply only to areas within the competence of the Union (i.e. trade and economic cooperation) and interstate competence (political and cultural cooperation). The ratification of all states is required for these agreements to enter into force. In addition, Article 228 § 3 (300 § 3) must be supported by the European Parliament accordingly, since these Agreements define both the institutional framework of cooperation operations and European treaties. [7, p. 405]

An important direction of TAS is the concept of "Partnership" which is mentioned in the name of the Agreement. This primarily determines the level of cooperation of the EU with new countries that did not exist before. Unlike trade agreements and cooperation agreements, the purpose of TAC is to create a legal basis for the development of closer cooperation in certain areas (culture, environmental protection, etc.). [2]

Unlike the European agreements, the TEA did not provide for the possibility of partner states joining the EU and privileged relations between the parties. From this it can be concluded that there could not be any special relationship between one of the EU members and the TAC signatory. None of the Partner States will seek closer cooperation, in contrast to the UK, France's relations with the ACP (Africa, Asia, Caribbean) and Mediterranean regions, which act as the locomotive of rapprochement. However, the concept of partnership included in the Agreement will play an important role in the relations of the European states included in the Union with the post-Soviet states, including the countries of the South Caucasus and Central Asia. After the collapse of the communist bloc and the beginning of the expansion of the EU, there was a danger of the emergence of a new dividing line between the European and CIS states. A new political, economic, social, and cultural separation could arise that would replace the "iron curtain" of the Cold War era.

Therefore, one of the main goals of TAS is to create conditions for regional integration. Despite the fact that the agreements were bilateral, the EU was trying to establish more reliable relations in the territory of the CIS. The Council noted that Partnership and Cooperation Agreements by the European Union are important

in the integration processes in the region. The preamble texts of the agreements mention the importance of political dialogue in "regulating conflicts in the region and ending contradictions", which in turn will help strengthen security in Europe. [See TAS preamble. 7, p. 406]

The role of agreements in the foreign policy process

Agreements will serve regional integrations, which will play an important role in the development of states. The agreements serve both integration and could have led to the desire of the South Caucasus states to join the EU. By creating sufficient time and conditions for such inclusion, TAS was included in the scheme of "integration of concentric circles" of the European integration processes. The probability of such a desire being more or less determines the possibility of diversification of approaches by the European Union.

The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement consisted of 12 chapters, 105 articles and 5 annexes. Only 2 pages of the 70-page Agreement discuss the tools of political dialogue.

Articles I and II of the agreement, which envisage the characteristics of partnership, did not leave room for political issues regarding the general principles of the development of relations. Most of the text is devoted to technical measures that ensure the development of economic relations that the EU and partner states will adopt. It is also interesting that certain provisions were made in the creation of favorable conditions in the field of trade, which could create an unexpected threat by restricting the trade of the partner state. During parallel negotiations under the TSA, partner states agreed to restrictions on certain categories of exports.[12] As an example, in July 1999, Kazakhstan and the European Coal and Steel Association reached an agreement on limiting steel exports from Kazakhstan. This operation was carried out in parallel with the entry into force of the partnership and cooperation agreement. This example reflects the challenge of economic convergence through trade and investment, a traditional interest of the European Union. In such a case, TAS determines the political dialogue of strengthening and deepening cooperation between the parties. The purpose of such a dialogue is to serve the convergence of positions on international issues. The common goal of rapprochement is to establish stability and security in the region and in general. The instruments of the political dialogue defined at the highest level are clearly indicated in the text of the Agreement.[9]

The political dialogue is carried out within the framework of the cooperation of the Councils implementing the Agreement. The Council meets once a year and is chaired by a member of the government of one of the countries that have signed the Agreement or a representative of the European Commission (the presidents of the Council are changed on a rotating basis). [10] When any contradictions arise in the implementation or interpretation of the agreement, the party could apply to the Council with a request to review them. In such cases, the resolution of the Council was of a rec-

ommendatory nature. In the period between the sessions of the Council, the committees on cooperation at the level of officials functioned.

Even the members of the EU Commission welcomed such critical remarks: "It is important to have the opportunity to solve the issues at the political level. We meet once a year, the discussion problem is the same. I take a critical approach to this and say that there is little progress. [13, p. 129]

In the opinion of authorized employees, in order to make important changes possible, the European Commission should specify the intended directions. "In order to understand what we will achieve in relations with the states, we need to compile a list of questions. It's not easy." [11]

Realization of the political dialogue is carried out within the framework of the parliamentary commissions uniting the members of the parliaments of the countries that have signed the Agreement and the members of the European Parliament, except for the representatives of the parliaments of the EU countries.[11] The purpose of the Commission's work is to observe the work of the Council and various departments of the Commission, the ministries of the countries that have signed the Agreement. The value of such inter-parliamentary interaction lies primarily in the fact that it enables European parliamentary committees to establish a regular dialogue with their counterparts in the region. An important aspect of this is that the information Europeans have about these regions is very superficial and incomplete. [14]

In addition, the fact that the political dialogue within the framework of the TAC is aimed at providing a greater image of the EU's activities in the South Caucasus should not be overlooked. [15]

In addition to the instruments considered above, the political nature of the TAS for dialogue, the rule of law, respect for human rights and minorities, are considered important conditions for cooperation. The agreements refer to the Helsinki Convention and the New European Charter of Paris for human rights. It should be noted that the Agreements provide for strict compliance with the requirements set in this area. Otherwise, the implementation of the Agreement may be formally suspended. Thus, the authors of the Agreement perceived human rights as an honest determination of their position on the one hand, and as a touchstone of the foreign policy being formed on the other hand.

In other words, the Agreement can be viewed as a political recommendation that can influence the integration process within the framework of the European Union's policy in the region. However, the practical side of the "political conditionality" factor was lagging behind the theoretical side. Thus, the standardized process did not allow the Council and the Commission to refuse to sign the Agreement, as its appropriateness and relevance to the region were questioned: "The continuing hesitation in the attitude towards the South Caucasus republics was explained in the document submitted by the Commission to the Council in September 1994. This paper questions whether the conditions set forth in the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement can meet

the high enough requirements in reality and that there are known difficulties and will face problems in meeting the conditions of the EU. Despite these problems, the TAS was signed and started to be implemented as a legal basis.

One of the tools used by the EU in its relations with the states is the reconciliation of economic aid and cooperation with political conditions (criterion of political conditionality). method is called. However, according to the words of the direct participants of the European Union foreign policy process, "during the existence of such tools, their activity was not stopped." [11. etc. 14]

The amount of costs related to agreements is not always estimated by the state budget.

According to the officials involved in this process, the signing of the TAS proves the clarification of the strategy both in the region and in the European institutions. "We have a tool that proves that the strategy does not exist. "Partnership and Cooperation Agreement is a typical example of this". [12]

However, from another point of view, the format created by TAS is "a rare context for bilateral political relations". The political will of both sides can be the basis for achieving the set goals.

However, the goals set by the European Union have not been fully revealed. The main dilemma the EU faces in the region is the choice between stability and democracy. If the EU's real interest is access to and transport of energy resources, this choice will prevent its interests from being realized. If the main subject of the problem is the fight against terrorism, then it is necessary to move away from democratic reforms. [13]

However, we see that the main factor in the EU's South Caucasus policy remains economic aid. The prospect of the South Caucasus states becoming a member has not yet been observed.

It prompts us to agree with the following conclusion about the nature and role of TPP in the EU policy in the South Caucasus under review: "Partnership and cooperation agreements" are ineffective but structured and adequate agreements. [8, p. 129]

After the South Caucasus states entered the "New Neighborhood" program, a new stage in the "Partnership and Cooperation Agreement" activity begins. The ten-year contract would be replaced by new agreements in a new format.

A revision of the cooperation format resulted in the TACIS program in 2007 and the end of the EU's "post-Soviet" approach to the region.

In general, the purpose of TAS is to serve the development of security, stability and prosperous living in the region on the basis of strong mutually beneficial cooperation. In addition, the agreement was intended as a long-term strategy of the EU in the South Caucasus. It is a strategy of large-scale economic aid and cooperation, formally regulated by a number of political conditions. From this point of view, the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement is an important and to some extent indirect tool of the common foreign policy of the European Union. The signing of the TAC provided the EU with a strategy and instrument base to develop the

relationship. It created the required legal basis for cooperation of the EU, which affects the policy in the region. [3, p. 318]

It is clear that despite the complex nature of the Agreement, their implementation and cooperation with the regional states is within the competence of the Union. The Commission was given more powers to finalize the negotiations on the agreements. It created an opportunity for the European Commission to act as a "diplomatic representative" of the European Union. This led to an increase in the EU's political weight in international forums. [10]

Thus, as a "foreign policy activity", TAS is intended to serve the development of large-scale political issues defined in Article J-1 (j.n.11) of the Treaty of European Union. [13]

The analysis of the instruments of cooperation between the European Union and the South Caucasus states made it possible to identify a number of features specific to European policy in this direction and to distinguish two phases of European policy formed in 1993-2001: [10]

First: 1993-1996 is the period of development and implementation of economic aid programs. During this period, the policy was implemented with the advantage of a pan-regional approach based on the economic interests of the EU in the region. All means of cooperation are concentrated in the hands of the European Commission, with minimal attention from the EU member states. The EU Commission was trying to solve a number of political issues by using economic instruments. The EU wanted to strengthen its leading position in the foreign policy process by establishing regional cooperation and settling conflicts. [10]

In 1996-2001, covering the second period, the "Partnership and Cooperation Agreement" was signed and entered into force. At this stage, the Council paid more attention to the activity of the Commission in the considered direction and tried to influence the ongoing processes. Despite the two-sided nature of TAS, its modified character continued to prevail in a generalized view of the region.

The entry of the South Caucasian states into the Council of Europe in 1999 and the events of September 11, 2001 were external factors that determined the transition to a new stage of cooperation. At the same time, a number of internal changes were taking place in the Council of Europe itself, which led to a change in the format and nature of relations.

During President Ilham Aliyev's visit to Brussels on July 11, 2018, the document entitled "Azerbaijan-European Union Partnership Priorities" was initialed by the Minister of Foreign Affairs E. Mammadyarov and the High Representative of the European Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy Federica Mogherini. The initialing ceremony was marked by the presence of President Ilham Aliyev and President of the Council of the European Union Donald Tusk. The Partnership Priorities document was essentially prepared to replace the European Neighborhood Policy Action Plan adopted in 2006 between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the European Union.

The document covers 4 priorities in accordance with the directions of cooperation established during the 2015 Riga summit of the Eastern Partnership. These priorities include strengthening institutions, good governance, economic development, market opportunities, connectivity, energy efficiency, environment, climate action, and finally, mobility and people-to-people connections.[5,p.148]

Conclusion

From the above, it can be concluded that the promising directions of cooperation between the parties have further developed during the period since the signing of the Agreement. According to Ambassador Kestutis Jankauskas, the representative of the European Union in Azerbaijan, Brussels focuses on cooperation with Azerbaijan in areas such as "green economy", small entrepreneurship, development of regions, support of education and healthcare. These were intended to help sustainable development in Azerbaijan. However, we know that TAS was signed for a period of 10 years and since the implementation period of the agreement ended in 2009, its implementation is extended for 1 month every year. Today, Azerbaijan and the European Union are on the verge of signing a new agreement. On June 26, 2021, the heads of foreign affairs of the three countries of the European Union - Austria, Latvia, Romania, Alexander Shallenberg, Gabrilliks Landsbergis and Bogdan Aurescu visited the South Caucasus on the instructions of the EU High Representative for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, Joseph Borrell. During the visit, the ministers visited Azerbaijan, Armenia, and then Georgia. Romanian Foreign Minister Bogdan Aurescu said at a press conference held in Tbilisi: "While in Azerbaijan, we expressed our belief that this country has a key role in the stability and prosperity of the South Caucasus. We hope that the new agreement currently being discussed between Azerbaijan and the EU will be signed by the end of this year."

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